

Title: Chief Legal Officer of DBMC, Lawyer.

Name: Cloudesley Rook-Hobbs

Affiliation: Dominion Bitcoin Mining Company Ltd.

INTRODUCTION:

Legally defining cryptocurrencies (in particular Ethereum and Bitcoin) within the Canadian Legal context. The legal definition of a cryptocurrency not only determines under which regulatory regime it will fall, but also determine who has the jurisdiction to make those regulations.

AIM:

To legally define different types of cryptocurrency within in a Canadian legal context.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

By reviewing and applying Canadian and other common-law cases and statutes that provide legal tests and definitions of goods, contracts, securities, property, intangibles, commodities, service contracts, money, etc.

RESULTS:

Not all cryptocurrencies are equal and the function of the coin will determine it legal standing. Under Canadian law bitcoins should be treated as commodities and as such fall under provincial regulation. There is however room for argument for them to be classified as “money” and therefore the exclusive purview of the Federal Government. That bitcoin transactions can support other types of operations however may impact on the legal treatment based on the users use of the coin. Ethereum most closely resembles a service contract and as such falls under concurrent federal and provincial jurisdiction and regulation. However also like bitcoin the courts may consider the users use of the coin to determine its standing on a case by case basis.

CONCLUSIONS:

Currently both federal and provincial bodies have taken steps to regulate cryptocurrencies, however this may open the door for jurisdictional challenges by defendants charged with regulatory offences and increased legal uncertainty when it comes to dealing with cryptocurrencies. The lack of clarity in existing regulations and the lack of a clear legal definition has left many cryptocurrency investors and companies no choice, but to operate in a legal grey-zone. This legal grey-zone has caused an industry chill in Canada and not provided the consumer protection promised by the regulations currently imposed. The regulators (both federal and provincial) should work together in establishing clear and reasonable legal definitions by statute for cryptocurrencies. That definition should also fit within the established common-law precedents on commodities, securities and money.

KEYWORDS:

Cryptocurrency, bitcoin, ethereum, law, regulations, blockchain, jurisdiction

BIOGRAPHY:

Cloudesley Hobbs

Chief Legal Officer of DBMC

Cloudesley J. C. R. Hobbs, B.F.A., J.D. graduated from Queen's University of Ontario with a Juris Doctorate in Law. Cloudesley practices law in Saskatchewan where he has worked in both private practice and with the Saskatchewan's Ministry of Justice's Civil Law Division, dealing primarily in litigation. Cloudesley has represented Bitcoin companies before tribunals, the Court of Queen's Bench, and Court of Appeal. He is the first lawyer in Canada to successfully represent a Bitcoin company against the Securities Commission of Saskatchewan. In addition to his legal practice, he is also an artist and was a Resident Artist for University of Regina's Faculty of Media Art and Performance in 2016. Cloudesley has been working with the blockchain industry clients for approximately 3 years.